

Computational Method to Detect and Measure Basic Influence Roles in Directed Networks

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Abstract

Within social networks, identifying key actors involved in influence processes is crucial for understanding social dynamics. Considering the overlap between network-based definitions of influential roles and the computational cost of several detection methods, our study propose a formally defined set of *Basic Influence Roles (BIRs)*, built upon the most simple centrality measures, the indegree and outdegree centrality. To facilitate a reliable, objective and precise identification, we propose a deterministic algorithm, testing its behavior across both static and dynamic network structures using synthetic datasets. This computational method can support social scientists in investigating the overall social influence phenomenon, as well as to help the understanding of very large social graphs, where visualization tools are no longer able. We would also underline that further studies can extend this method in other scientific fields other than social sciences, where network analysis can be applied.

Keywords: influence network · network dynamics · social influence · social role · social network analysis · network science · scalable algorithm

1 Introduction

Social influence is a topic of great interest for the computational social sciences, and a multitude of models have been developed [1–3]. Along with other questions, research has focused on the role played by social actors in influencing others [4–8]. Social network analysis has contributed to study the phenomenon providing some useful concepts and methods to identify influential nodes [9, 10]. Centrality methods are widely adopted to detect them [10].

However, it is acknowledged the heterogeneity of many operative definitions of social roles, due, apart the different interpretations of edges, to the different methods employed [11]. Some definitions of influential nodes are based on the simplest centrality measure, but “in many applications, we need more informative measures” that, conversely, are not “simple to compute” [12].

The aim of our study is to define more rigorously social influence roles using degree centrality, keeping the description at a low level of complexity. In order to accomplish this goal and try to organize the basic definitions, we propose a formal categorization of *Basic Influence Roles (BIRs)* in a social digraph. With “basic”, we mean the roles that can be clusterable using only indegree and outdegree centrality. Then, starting from this definition, we propose to formulate a deterministic algorithm to detect these categories.

Beyond a more precise definition of which are the BIRs, this method could provide both a theoretical and applied contribution.

About the first, it can help in investigating the overall social influence phenomenon, and other related phenomena, in quantitative and mixed researches. It can also help to understand social networks where the visual exploration is more difficult due to their size [13]. Other scientific fields can extend this method to investigate phenomena based on network dynamics [14, 15].

In applied research, our research can be useful in multiple industry fields starting from marketing and communication [16–18]; for example, in the study of influence maximization, to design effective campaigns increasing reach and effectiveness with fewer resources [19]; in the study of influence minimization, for example to avoid or prevent disinformation or the spreading of malicious content [20];

2 Background and related works

Social Influence is defined as “intentional and unintentional efforts to change another person’s beliefs, attitudes, or behavior” [21]. A multitude of models have been developed in the social network literature to explain and predict the dynamics of social influence [1–3]. Mason, Conrey, and Smith proposed “four conceptual dimensions to delineate the universe of possible models”, based on two fundamental components: sources and targets of influence, if the model is unidirectional or multidirectional, and temporal dynamics, if model is static or dynamic over time [22].

Central to influence models is the identification of key actors in the influence process [23]. Two-Step Flow of Communication, a classic model proposed by Katz and Lazarsfeld in 1955, has suggested a two-stage process, considering the passage of information from the mass media to the “opinion leaders”, to then reach a wider audience made up of their followers [4–8]. However, social influence often follows more complex paths and involves multiple steps [24], as well as further studies has resized the role of influentials to trigger large information cascades [23]. We can say that every node in a social network plays a unique role, influencing others in their own way [25]. More in general, as described in Table 1, three main concepts of social roles have been reported in social network context: *Functionalist*, *Interactionist*, and *Systemic* [11]. Functionalist and Systemic are more widely adopted in online studies “considering the member’s behavior as being related to his position in the network” [11].

Approach	Description	Methodology
Functionalist	Role refers to the specific position or function that an individual or group plays in the social influence process.	Mainly quantitative
Interactionist	Situational dependent roles, as defined within interactions.	Qualitative
Systemic	Roles as a product of social interactions, but these interactions are guided by the structural social system.	Mainly mixed

Table 1: Concepts of social roles described by Benamar *et al.* [11].

Multiple social roles based on network properties have definitions that can be overlapped depending on the context and meaning [11], and a “further clarification of role conceptualization and operationalization are therefore still required” [11]. Methods used to define social influence roles are widely based on different centrality measures, leading to different operative definitions [10, 11, 26–30]. Motif detection algorithms are also employed to identify the influence of nodes in complex network [31, 32].

The basic definition of hub, using degree centrality [33], is “nodes with a huge number of links” [10]. However, this definition lost its specificity, becoming less useful as more categorizations have been introduced using further centrality methods, sometimes more computationally intensive [10–12, 26–30, 34]. Studies have developed centrality measures to identify roles in complex networks based on collective dynamics [35–37].

As observed by Kang *et al.* [12], “except for degree, the other two centrality measures, closeness and betweenness, are prohibitively expensive to compute, and thus impractical for large networks”. Graph databases can offer an efficient platform for calculating centrality measures due to their optimized structure [38–40]. However, in specific real-world scenarios, especially with huge network datasets, utilizing existing centrality algorithms directly might not be readily adaptable or maintain the same level of scalability achieved within appropriate graph processing systems [12, 41, 42]. This necessitates exploring alternative approaches or adaptations of centrality algorithms [12, 41].

3 Methodology

Our study is descriptive, the purpose is to provide a more basic, clear and precise description of *how* a social actor can influence others. To achieve this goal, we propose a formal definition of *Basic Influence Role (BIR)* as property of social entities within a social network.

Symbol	Description
<i>Social System</i> (G)	A directed graph composed of vertices (social entities) and edges (contacts or interactions between them).
<i>Social Entity</i> (v)	A social actor, such as individuals, media, organizations. Digital media users can be an example.
<i>Social Interactions</i> or <i>Social Contacts</i>	Edges between social entities, encompassing various forms of communication, engagement, or exchange, as well as social relationships or more in general incoming or outgoing contacts. Here we exclude self-loops connections, as they hold no meaning in our study.
<i>Indegree</i> (δ^+)	Number of incoming edges directed towards a specific social entity (v).
<i>Outdegree</i> (δ^-)	Number of outgoing edges originating from a specific social entity (v).
N	$V(G) - 1$, the total number of nodes minus 1. We subtract 1 to $V(G)$ because self-loops are excluded.
α	A constant, represented by the value 0.7, designating the slope of the lines demarcating the amplifier and reducer areas from the hub area.

Table 2: Notation of symbols.

Given notation in *Table 2*, we started generating an artificial dataset to cover all the space configurations of indegree and outdegree. The dataset consists in a degree matrix where each row is composed by three columns, representing indegree, outdegree, and a node’s identifier. The data was generated following three steps: at first, we created a set Z of integer values $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$; then we created two vectors as a collection of indegree (δ^+) and outdegree (δ^-), both containing all values of Z ; finally, we select all the permutations of ordered pairs (δ^+, δ^-) , including the index of the specific permutation as node’s identifier.

Figure 1: Clustered representation of BIRs (axis are normalized).

Figure 2: Example of distinct BIRs in a stochastic scale-free network (axis are normalized).

The definition of BIR was operationalized by mapping relevant concepts from the literature onto a two-dimensional space based on indegree and outdegree centrality measures. The x-axis represents outdegree (δ^-) and the y-axis represents indegree (δ^+). In this two-dimensional space, we have identified six distinct areas, each of which corresponds to six different role concepts (*Figure 1*). It is important to clarify that, while the minimum value of x and y is 0, the maximum values for both axes are determined by $V(G) - 1$, meaning the total number of vertices minus one (because self-loops edges are excluded), that is the maximum possible indegree or outdegree value within the specific network. Therefore, we underline that BIRs are network-specific: not all networks can encompass the entire spectrum of possible roles. We can observe an example in (*Figure 2*).

Figure 3: Clustered representation of BIRs' levels (axis are normalized).

Figure 4: BIRs' influence exerted in the network (axis are normalized).

To quantify the influence of every single node according to the assumed BIR, we used for every category a different normalized distance measure as defined in paragraph 4. Indicated with I , in a range from 0 to 1, this measure denotes respectively the absence of influence and the maximum BIR's influence relative to the specific network (Figure 4).

Additionally, we explored possible subcategorizations based on the influence measure. This led us to identify five useful areas (Figure 3), to formalize as levels assumed by an ordinal variable:

1. *None*: a total absence of influence, when $I = 0$.
2. *Branch*: the lowest influence related to that role, when $\delta^- \in \{0, 1\} \wedge \delta^+ \in \{0, 1\}$; it is a network motif called “dyad” or “triad chain” [31, 32]; the term “branch” is used in signal-flow graphs [43]; another name is “pendant vertex” or “leaf vertex” if a vertex has degree 1 in undirected graphs [44].
3. *Weak*: a weak influence related to that role, when $I \leq 0.5$.
4. *Strong*: a strong influence related to that role, when $I > 0.5$.
5. *Top*: the greatest influence related to that role, when $I = 1$.

These clusters and the influence measures were defined by deterministic mathematical functions, ensuring the *reliability*, and allowing us to build an influence detection algorithm [45]. This algorithm then was used to computationally test the mutual exclusivity of the distinct categories.

We analyzed data through an iterative approach that incorporates unit testing, visual inspection, and confusion matrices. This multi-pronged approach provided us a clear representation of non-overlapping between classes, a guide for iterative refinement of the mathematical definitions, and a comprehensive understanding of the algorithm's effectiveness. The algorithm implementation and the code used to generate the presented results is publicly available on GitHub [45].

4 Basic Influence Roles

Figure 5: A graph visualization of BIRs, tailored to enhance their characteristics.

BIR is a property of social entities and assumes six states: *Emitter*, *Amplifier*, *Hub*, *Reducer*, *Receiver*, *Isolated* (Figure 5). Given the notation in Table 2, we provide the following definitions of every role.

Figure 6: A graph visualization of branch levels. Only hub, emitter, and receiver roles have this subcategory.

4.1 Hub

We define “hub” a key entity with a balanced ratio between indegree and outdegree, or in other words a social entity balanced as production and reception of information (1). Inside this area we could identify the *top* hubs, the social entities with the greatest balance of incoming and outgoing interactions (if edges have the meaning of interactions); *strong* and *weak*, if this balance is respectively greater or lower than the average; *branch*, if both sources and receivers: what each of these nodes receives is sent to the next unique social entity to which is connected, having indegree and outdegree equal to 1. Certain interpretations of “bridges” as nodes connecting two disconnected groups, can be considered branches having the dual role of receiving and transmitting information [46].

The influence associated with this role, denoted by I_v , is quantified as the normalized sum of its indegree and outdegree, relative to the largest possible hub, having indegree and outdegree equal to N (2).

$$f(v) = \text{Hub, if } v \notin \text{other categories} \quad (1)$$

$$I_v = \frac{\delta^+ + \delta^-}{2N} \quad (2)$$

4.2 Amplifier

The term “amplifier” node was used with different meanings in the context of social influence and social media analytics [47]. Certain interpretations refer to “users who do not publish interesting content by themselves, but who have the potential to diffuse information published by others to many new people” [47], or as “an individual who collates multiple thoughts and shares ideas and opinions [...], the initial person to retweet a tweet – one which is part of a retweet chain” [48]. Analyzing the nature of communication flows during social conflicts, it has been defined as a type of communicator, lower in the communication hierarchy, who plays an intermediary role [8], or operationalized using bridge analysis in the context of social media analytics [49].

We define “amplifier” a node with significantly more outgoing connections than incoming ones (3). For this reason, it is a positive regulator, increasing for example the flow of information. It could be a social entity that listens little but talks too much, or it could act as a megaphone to the social entities to which it is connected.

The greatest possible multiplier effect is held by the *top* amplifiers, when the number of outgoing interactions is maximum, but there is only one ingoing interaction (if edges have the meaning of interactions). A *strong* multiplier effect, with many outgoing interactions and few ingoing ones. *Weak*, if there is only a discrete multiplier effect.

The influence I_v , related to this role is measured as the inverse of the normalized e-based exponential ratio between indegree and outdegree (4): higher this value, stronger the node’s amplifying effect.

$$f(v) = \text{Amplifier, if } \frac{\delta^+}{\delta^-} \leq \alpha \quad (3)$$

$$I_v = 1 - \left(\exp^{\frac{\delta^+}{\delta^-}} - \exp^{\frac{1}{N}} \right) \quad (4)$$

4.3 Reducer

This role is known also under the name of “gatekeeper”. Given that every agent in a network can be a “gatekeeper”, this type of node reduces, filters or block information, being a gate or channel through which information passes [50]. If the only existing channel that connect many sources with one or a few nodes, it is a *global* gatekeeper, otherwise a *local* gatekeeper [51].

We define “reducer” a node with significantly more incoming connections than outgoing ones (5): it is a negative regulator, for instance, making the flow of interactions decrease. It may also act as an information selector, collecting a lot of information to share what is most relevant, so as a big barrier to the spread of news for example. The *top* reducer is the node with the greatest possible selective effect, when the number of incoming interactions is maximum but there is only one outgoing interaction; *weak* if there is only a discrete selective effect.

The influence I_v related to this role is measured as the inverse of the normalized e-based exponential ratio between outdegree and indegree (6): higher this value, stronger the node’s reducing effect.

$$f(v) = \text{Reducer, if } \frac{\delta^-}{\delta^+} \leq \alpha \quad (5)$$

$$I_v = 1 - \left(\exp^{\frac{\delta^-}{\delta^+}} - \exp^{\frac{1}{N}} \right) \quad (6)$$

4.4 Emitter

Another concept is “source node”, indicating in social influence context the one (or among other source nodes) responsible to the entire information cascade in social networks [52]. It has been called “information starter” [47] and “idea starter” with the meaning of “an individual who starts a conversational meme” [48].

We define “emitter” a social entity that spreads information without receiving, having zero as constant value of indegree (7). This entity is active in producing information, but totally ignored by the incoming flow (or not exposed to it). *Top* if performs the maximum of interactions, *weak* if performs few incoming interactions. It can be an *emitter* branch when it is a source node, if indegree is zero and outdegree is one.

The influence associated with this role, denoted by I_v , is quantified simply as the normalized outdegree with respect to N (8).

$$f(v) = \text{Receiver, if } \delta^+ = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$I_v = \frac{\delta^+}{N} \quad (8)$$

4.5 Receiver

In literature multiple names are employed to indicate what we define as “receiver”. A “sink node”, having no outgoing connections, in the context of social influence, is a node that has no influence on other nodes but may be influenced by others [53]. Such node has been called “viewer”, “an individual who takes passive interest in the conversation” [48]; these typologies “do not share or create information online, they consume large amounts of information and share it with their offline network” [48].

We define “receiver” a social entity which receives only interactions, but does not produce any, having zero as constant value of outdegree (9). For example when a social entity absorbs a huge amount of information but is totally inactive in sharing. *Top* if receives the maximum of interactions, *weak* if receives few interactions; *receiver* branch, if only receives, with 0 outdegree and 1 as indegree.

The influence associated with this role, denoted by I_v , is quantified simply as the normalized indegree with respect to N (10).

$$f(v) = \text{Receiver, if } \delta^- = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$I_v = \frac{\delta^-}{N} \quad (10)$$

4.6 Isolated

An “isolated vertex” is a well known type of node in network science [10]. We define “*isolated*” a totally non-participatory (or totally disconnected) social entity, with zero for indegree and outdegree (11). For this reason, the influence I_v related to this role has the default value of 0 (12).

$$f(v) = \text{Isolated, if } \delta^+ = \delta^- = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$I_v = 0 \quad (12)$$

5 BIRs in synthetic networks

We explored the behavior of BIRs detection algorithm across different social network structures, applying it on a selection of synthetic datasets encompassing various network types. The aim is only to observe the patterns of data. The first describes the distribution of BIRs across six static directed networks. The second is aimed to describe the temporal evolution of BIRs within a dynamic directed network. The code used to produce the following results is publicly available on GitHub [45].

5.1 Distribution of BIRs in static networks

We report in *Figure 7* the distribution of BIRs across six static directed networks. These synthetic datasets, each having 100 nodes, were produced using different graph algorithms. The first two are based on *Erdős-Rényi* model [54, 55], having respectively 103 and 457 edges with 0.01 and 0.05 as edge creation’s probability. The others are *Scale-Free* [56] with 207 edges, *Watts-Strogatz Small-World* [57] with 100 edges, *Navigable Small World* [58] with 229 edges, and *Random Rooted Forest* [59, 60] with 98 edges.

Figure 7: Distribution of BIRs in six different static networks.

The *Erdős-Rényi 1* exhibits a relatively balanced distribution across most roles, with values ranging from 0.12 (reducer) to 0.28 (emitter). About isolated, only this dataset shows a moderate presence, while a total absence for the others. *Erdős-Rényi 2*, in contrast to the previous case, shows a dominant presence of hubs (0.44) and amplifiers (0.34), with a lower prevalence of emitters (0.01) and receivers

(0.02). *Scale-Free* network shows a strong predominance of emitters (0.75) and a low occurrence of other roles (all below 0.1). *Watts-Strogatz Small World* network exhibits a high concentration of hubs (0.78) along with a moderate presence of emitters (0.1) and reducers (0.06). *Navigable Small World* network shows a dominant presence of hubs (0.55) alongside a significant presence of amplifiers (0.23) and reducers (0.22) and a complete absence of emitters and receivers. *Random Rooted Forest* network shows a balanced distribution with a higher prevalence of emitters and receivers (0.37) compared to other roles.

Figure 8: Heatmaps showing the distribution of BIRs' levels across six different static networks. The letters *T*, *S*, *W*, *B*, *N* respectively stand for *Top*, *Strong*, *Weak*, *Branch*, and *None*.

Observing the distributions of BIRs' levels (Figure 8), *Erdős-Rényi 1* network reveals a predominance of branch-level roles across all categories. The distribution within all roles exhibits a relative balance amongst weak subcategories for all roles. In addition, amplifiers and reducers demonstrate a low percentage of nodes classified as strong. *Erdős-Rényi 2* shows a significant portion (0.43) of nodes exhibit weak hub role. The network presents a balanced mix of strong (0.12) and weak (0.22) amplifiers, while less prevalent, a small proportion of nodes (0.14 strong, 0.05 weak) acting as reducers. Only a minimal percentage (0.02) of nodes fall into the weak receiver category. In *Scale Free* network emitters exhibit a clear predominance, manifested in both weak (0.31) and branch (0.44) subcategories. Amplifiers and reducers display a similar pattern, characterized by consistently low values across both strong and weak subcategories. Hubs and receivers also demonstrate a comparable pattern, with low representation within both weak and branch levels. In *Watts-Strogatz Small World* network, hubs are exclusively observed in the branch sub-level, constituting 0.78 of nodes classified as hubs. All other roles appear predominantly within the weak subcategory, with the sole exception of emitters, where a small proportion (0.09) fall into the branch level. *Navigable Small World* dataset exhibits only amplifiers, hubs, and reducers, all exclusively within the weak subcategory. Finally, the *Random Rooted Forest* network presents some similarities to *Erdős-Rényi 1* dataset, emitters exhibit a balanced distribution between branch and weak levels. The role of amplifier, like in datasets *Erdős-Rényi 1* and *Scale Free*, has a weak presence. Both hub and reducer roles show a moderate presence within the network. The receiver role exhibits a combined presence of weak and branch levels.

5.2 Distribution of BIRs in a dynamic network

In Figure 9 we report the distribution of BIRs over time in a dynamic network. The dataset was generated using an *Independent Cascade Model* [61–63] to simulate a temporal network with evolving interactions.

The simulation proceeded through 12 time steps, and starting from a *Erdős-Rényi's* network of 100 nodes with 0.01 as edge creation's probability. At each step, new edges were added with a constant probability of 0.2. The probability of removing an existing edge varied across time steps, starting with a higher probability of 0.4 and gradually decreasing to 0.99 in a specific sequence (0.4, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9, 0.94, 0.96, 0.7, 0.9, 0.9, 0.94, 0.99). This design is aimed to simulate alternating periods of high and low network activity, culminating in a near-complete inactivation of information flow within the network.

Figure 9: Distribution of BIRs in a dynamic network.

We can describe the dynamic evolution of BIRs in 5 phases. The initial stage (*Time Step 1*) shows a balanced distribution of roles with a predominance of emitters and receivers. We also observe a small percentage of isolated nodes (0.09). In the second period (*Time Steps 2-4*) the information flow is only handled exclusively by hubs (0.53-0.62), followed by amplifiers and reducers. In the third stage (*Time Steps 5-7*) the number of hubs decreases towards a more balanced distribution across roles. Here several nodes become progressively inactives (from 0 to 0.24). In the last stage (*Time Steps 8-12*), we observe a transition from a distribution exclusively represented by hubs, amplifiers and reducers, to a more balanced scenario, to shift, in the end, towards inactivity, with a predominance of isolated nodes (0.7).

6 Conclusions

In this study we have presented a formal definition of *Basic Influence Roles (BIRs)* based on indegree and outdegree centrality measures, aimed to describe *how* a social actor can influence others. Our analysis categorize BIRs into six types: *Emitter*, *Amplifier*, *Hub*, *Reducer*, *Receiver*, and *Isolated*. A measure of influence is associated to each category and, based on this value, we provided a further subcategorization: *None*, *Branch*, *Weak*, *Strong*, and *Top*.

Future research can explore the BIRs' applicability in real-world scenarios. Evaluating BIRs' behavior on real-world static and dynamic networks could provide valuable insights into their effectiveness in capturing influence dynamics within complex systems. In particular, the proposed categorization can be employed to examine a variety of social network phenomena, starting from information diffusion, opinion formation, and social contagion.

It is important to acknowledge some limitations associated with this approach. Firstly, the proposed role descriptions are only applicable to directed graphs, and does not take in consideration the edge's weight. Another limitation is to recognize that the employed centrality measures represents the most basic form of such metrics. While offering a straightforward starting point, this may lead to an oversimplified understanding of node roles, not only in general, but particularly within the context of a quantitative approach [64]. Finally, also if we can study the distribution of BIRs over time, the method adopts a static perspective, failing to capture the dynamic nature of network interactions [22].

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